

Correction to: Impact on granular bed: validation of discrete element modeling results by means of two-dimensional finite element analysis

Valentina Marzulli¹ · Luis Armando Torres Cisneros¹ · Annamaria di Lernia² · Christopher Robert Kit Windows-Yule³ · Francesco Cafaro² · Thorsten Pöschel¹

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The article “Impact on granular bed: validation of discrete element modelling results by means of two-dimensional finite element analysis” written by Valentina Marzulli, Luis Armando Torres Cisneros, Annamaria di Lernia, Christopher Robert Kit Windows-Yule, Francesco Cafaro, Thorsten Pöschel was originally published Online First without Open Access. After publication in volume 22, issue 1, article 27 the author decided to opt for Open Choice and to make the article an Open Access publication. Therefore, the copyright of the article has been changed to © The Author(s) 2020 and the article is forthwith distributed under the terms of the

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The original article has been corrected.

The original article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10035-019-0988-1>.

✉ Valentina Marzulli
valentina.marzulli@fau.de

Luis Armando Torres Cisneros
luis.torres@fau.de

Annamaria di Lernia
annamaria.dilernia@poliba.it

Christopher Robert Kit Windows-Yule
c.r.windows-yule@bham.ac.uk

Francesco Cafaro
francesco.cafaro@poliba.it

Thorsten Pöschel
thorsten.poeschel@fau.de

¹ Institute for Multiscale Simulation, Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Cauerstrasse 3, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

² Department of Civil, Environmental, Land, Building Engineering and Chemistry, Politecnico di Bari, Via Orabona 4, 70125 Bari, Italy

³ School of Chemical Engineering, University of Birmingham, Edgbaston, Birmingham B15 2TT, UK

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